

THE EFFECTS OF SHEAR RESISTANCE AT FIBER ENDS
ON THE DAMAGE PROPAGATION

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ABSTRACT

The microscopic damage propagation at fiber ends is examined in broken (short) fiber composite materials. Four microscopic failure modes of debonding and matrix cracking are discussed numerically based upon the fracture criteria including the Griffith's energy equation of the failure, where the irreversible process such as plastic deformation or slip is incorporated. A modified shear lag method is used to accommodate the shear stress along the debonded interface and the non-zero axial force in the matrix and to yield the critical load as a function of the debonding length for various geometrical and material constants. The load deformation curves are also presented.

INTRODUCTION

Short fiber reinforced composite materials are expected to use extensively in the future automotive industries and many kinds of studies have been performed. The fracture toughness property is especially important for the safety of structure or under the dynamic loading condition where

Figure 1. Debonding at (a)broken and (b)short fiber ends and (c)their various failure modes.

the material usually presents the brittle behavior. The toughness is considered to be related to the microscopic failure processes in composite materials, though the most studies on strength and fracture of these materials are based on the macroscopic experimental investigations. In broken or short fiber composites the microscopic damage initiates at or near the fiber ends (see Fig.1(a)(b)) and propagates in the matrix as a crack or along the interface between the matrix and fiber as a debonding. When the crack in the matrix intersects a fiber, higher stresses at the crack tip may cause fiber fracture or tensile separation and/or shear failure at the interface, resulting in fiber pullout or fiber bridging[1]. Fig.1(c) shows the fundamental patterns of the microscopic failure to be considered in the present paper. Mode A is the debonding along the interface starting from the edge of the fiber. Modes B and C accompany the crack propagation at the debonding tip and fiber ends, respectively. Debonding occurs also along the neighboring interfaces in Mode D. The amount of these damages is very important for the toughness of composites especially under the shear resistance. These modes are supposed to be governed by the stress distributions which are affected by the shear resistance along the debonded interface, debonding length, geometrical conditions, and material constants especially the Young's modulus ratio between fiber and matrix.

Recently these microscopic failure processes were discussed theoretically in unidirectional composite materials[2-4] with the use of both the modified shear lag analysis and the Griffith type energy equation for failure. In references[2-4] three fiber model was used where the outer fibers are infinitely long. Thus the complete debonding around the center broken fiber makes the effective Young's modulus of damaged composite materials as almost two-third of the initial one. In this paper all fibers are assumed to be short as shown in Fig.2(a). A modified shear lag method devel-

Figure 2. Broken (short) fiber composites modelling and details, (a) and (b), respectively, with (c) debonding shear resistance τ_{1D} .

oped in [2-4] is applied to the unit area in Fig.2(b) with the shear resistance originating from the plastic deformation, slip in Fig.2(c), or others [5] to yield the realistic load deformation curves of composites up to the final stage of failure. Recent extensions of the shear lag model relate to stress transfer across the fiber end[6], adhesion friction or slip process based on plasticity[7,8], thermal and chemical shrinkage or Poisson's contraction[5], chemico-physical interactions[9], and the Griffith type concept on debonding[2-4]. Next the theoretical model will be described, which accomodates the shear stress along the debonded interface and the non-zero axial force in the matrix, and is appropriate to discuss the failure modes in Fig.1.

THEORETICAL MODEL

The broken (short) fiber length, debonding length, fiber width, matrix width, and the thickness of the model are denoted by $4L$, $2a$, t , h , and t_0 , respectively, as shown in Fig.2. The suffixes, 2, 1, and m, denote the upper and lower fibers and matrix, respectively. The axial force p_i and the shear stress along the interface related to the fiber "i" τ_i are represented with the use of both the characteristic displacement u_i along the center of each phase and the matrix displacement u_m^i at the interface as follows,

$$p_i = E_f t t_0 \frac{du_i}{dx}, \quad p_m = E t t_0 \left(\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{du_m^2}{dx} + 2 \frac{du_m^1}{dx} + \frac{du_m^1}{dx} \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_1 = \frac{2G}{h} (u_m - u_m^1), \quad \tau_2 = \frac{2G}{h} (u_m^2 - u_m) \quad (2)$$

where G , E , and E_f are the shear modulus of the matrix and Young's moduli of the matrix and fiber, respectively, and

$$u_m^1 = u_m - \frac{\tau_1 D h}{2G} \quad (0 < x < a), \quad u_1 \quad (a < x < L), \quad u_m^2 = u_2. \quad (3)$$

Here the matrix displacement varies bilinearly along the y -direction and the fiber displacement is a function of only x . Inserting eqs.(1) and (2) with eq.(3) into the following equilibrium equations:

$$\frac{dp_1}{dx} + 2\tau_1 t_0 = 0, \quad \frac{dp_2}{dx} - 2\tau_2 t_0 = 0, \quad \frac{dp_m}{dx} + (\tau_2 - \tau_1) t_0 = 0 \quad (4)$$

leads to the basic equations of the present problem. Applying the boundary conditions at both $x=0$ and L :

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_2 = u_m = 0, \quad p_1 = 0 & \quad (x = 0), \\
 u_m = u_L, \quad u_1 + u_2 = 2u_L & \quad (x = L),
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

and the continuity conditions at $x=a$ for the displacements and forces to the basic equations yields yields the solution, which is similar to the one in [3] and is not described here due to the limitation of pages. For later use the rigidity ratio β and the non-dimensional values of x , matrix displacement at $x=L$, u_L , τ_i , and p_m as ξ , u_L^* , τ_i^* , and p_m^* , respectively, are defined as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \beta &= \frac{Eh}{E_f t}, & \xi &= x \left(\frac{2G}{E_f th} \right)^{1/2}, \\
 u_L^* &= u_L \left(\frac{2GE_f t}{h} \right)^{1/2} \frac{t_0}{p_f}, & \tau_i^* &= \tau_i \left(\frac{E_f th}{2G} \right)^{1/2} \frac{t_0}{p_f}, \\
 (i) \quad (i) & & & \\
 p_m^* &= \frac{p_m}{\beta p_f} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{du_2^*}{d\xi} + 3 \frac{du_m^*}{d\xi} \right) & (0 < x < a), \\
 &= \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{du_2^*}{d\xi} + 2 \frac{du_m^*}{d\xi} + \frac{du_1^*}{d\xi} \right) & (a < x < L).
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Here u_i follows the same conversion as u_L to yield u_i^* , and p_f is the representative force and taken to be the total force p_T divided by $(1+\beta)$ in this paper except Fig.3.

MICROSCOPIC FAILURE CRITERION

Comparison Between Different Composite Systems

Non-dimensional values are not appropriate for the comparison between composite materials with different E_f . Composite materials without the microscopic failure are expected to support the load proportional to their rigidity. Thus p_T of $0.01(E_f t + Eh)t_0$ is applied to the unit of the model except Fig.6. The load required for each failure $p_{T,c}$ defines the critical load factor K as,

$$K = \frac{p_{T,c}}{0.01(E_f t + Eh)t_0} \tag{7}$$

Griffith's Criterion for Debonding with Shear Strength

The increase of the total potential energy δU_T with the extension of the debonding δa is

$$\begin{aligned}\delta U_T &= \delta U_{SUR} + \delta U_W + \delta U_{SE} + \delta U_P \\ &= \delta U_{SUR} - \delta U_e\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

$$\delta U_e = - (\delta U_W + \delta U_{SE} + \delta U_P) \quad (9)$$

where δU_{SUR} , δU_P , δU_{SE} , and δU_W denote the increases in the surface energy, potential energy of the applied load, strain energy, and irreversible work used in the process such as the plastic deformation or slip shown in Fig.2 (c), and δU_e is the effective energy which could be used for the newly debonded interface. In the present problem these are as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}\delta U_{SUR} &= 2\gamma_B t_0 \delta a, & \delta U_W &= \frac{\partial}{\partial a} \left\{ \int_0^a (-\tau_{1D}) t_0 (u_1 - u_m^1) dx \right\} \delta a \\ \delta U_{SE} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial a} \left\{ \int_0^a \frac{1}{2} (-\tau_{1D}) t_0 (u_m^1 - u_1) dx + \frac{1}{2} (0.5p_2 + p_m) u_L \right\} \delta a \\ & & & x=2L \text{ (or } 0) \\ \delta U_P &= \frac{\partial}{\partial a} \left\{ \int_0^a (-\tau_{1D}) t_0 (u_m^1 - u_1) dx \right\}\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

where γ_B is the specific surface energy of the debonded interface. Inserting eq.(10) into eq.(8) and setting $\delta U_T=0$ yields $p_{T,c}$ based on the energy criterion for the relatively large ratio of u_L^* to τ_{1D}^* . A practical process to obtain K will be mentioned in the next section.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Material constants and geometrical parameters given in Table 1 are used. The E_f and a quarter of the fiber aspect ratio L/t are taken as the parameters and τ_{1D} is too in the case of the maximum stress criteria.

Fig.3 shows the effects of a/t on the axial force and shear stress distributions for both $\tau_{1D}/\tau_{1T}=0$ and 1, which is the ratio of the shear stress along the debonded region to the maximum one at the debonding tip, $x=a+0$. The p_m^* has its peak at $x=a$ (debonding tip) and 0 (fiber end) for $\tau_{1D}=0$ and

TABLE 1
Material constants and geometrical parameters

Young's Modulus of Fiber	E_f^*	390	GPa
Young's Modulus of Matrix	E_f^f	3.5	GPa
Shear Rigidity of Matrix	G	1.25	GPa
Fiber Width	t	10×10^{-6}	m
Matrix Width	h	10×10^{-6}	m
Quarter Aspect Ratio	L/t^*	10	
Surface Energy	γ_B	160	J/m ² [10]
Shear Resistance	τ_{1D}^*	35	MPa

*: if not mentioned otherwise.

Figure 3. Effects of debonding shear resistance τ_{1D} and half debonding length a/t on the (a) axial force and (b) shear stress distribution along the x -axis in the matrix for $E_f = 390$ GPa and $L/t = 10$ under $u_L^* = 1$.

1, respectively. The inverse of the peak p_m^* is proportional to the critical load factor K based upon the maximum normal stress criterion, which is related to the matrix cracking, Modes B and C in Fig.1. The shear resistance decreases the shear stress concentration, especially for the large a/t , though the peak always appears at the debonding tip. The τ_2 is smaller than τ_1 and approaches to the maximum τ_1 for $\tau_{1D} = \tau_{1T}$ and large a/t , which is related to Mode D. The inverse of τ_1^* at the debonding tip leads to the critical load factor K based upon the maximum shear stress criterion and related to Mode A. The SI units is used in the following figures.

Fig.4 shows K for the matrix cracking obtained from Fig.3(a). There

Figure 4. Critical load factor K for matrix cracking under $\sigma_c = \sigma_m$ as a function of a/t with the parameters of τ_{1D} , a quarter of fiber aspect ratio L/t , and fiber Young's modulus E_f .

is the peak of K for $\tau_{1D} = 0$. The σ_c is the critical value of the normal stress in the matrix, σ_m .

Fig.5(a) shows the effects of a/t on the effective energy $\sqrt{\delta U_e / \delta a}$ as a function of τ_{1D} . The energy decreases as a/t increasing for small a/t and increases for large a/t . The a/t at this turning point depends on τ_{1D} . Fig.5(b) shows the process to obtain the critical load factor $K(K^*)$ based upon the Griffith type energy equation. The K^* is used in this figure as p_t of $(E_f t + Eh)t_0$ is applied to the model in Fig.5. When the shear resistance and effective energy corresponding to the surface energy are given (Steps 1 and 2) the master curve (solid line) is expanded to a chained line. The K^* is obtained in Step 3. The K is obtained in a similar manner.

Figs.6 and 7 show the load deformation curves based upon the maximum shear stress criterion and Griffith type energy equation, respectively. The critical load factor K is taken as an ordinate and the displacement of the matrix at $x=L$ is as an abscissa. The effects of L/t and E_f are shown. To compare the curves for various L/t , u_L is normalized by multiplying $10t/L$. The debonding propagation process is indicated with a/t on the curves. It is pointed out that there is a peak value for K at $\tau_{1D} = 0$ in the case of

Figure 5. The square root of the specific effective energy $\sqrt{\delta U_e / \delta a}$ with the parameter of a/t and τ_{1D} for (a) $E_f = 390$ GPa and $L/t = 10$, and (b) its use to obtain the critical load factor K (K^*) based upon the Griffith type energy criterion.

the maximum shear stress criterion. The τ_c is the critical shear stress. The value of γ_B is the one of epoxy[10]. The Griffith type energy criterion yields the peak of K in the wide range of parameters.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The followings are obtained by applying the modified shear lag model to the microscopic damage model for broken (short) fiber composite materials.

- 1) The shear resistance of the debonded interface tends to make the Mode A stable, otherwise it propagates unstably at the critical a/t as shown in Fig.6. The Griffith type of energy equation presents the critical a/t in the wide range of parameters for the unstable propagation of Mode A.
- 2) Modes B and C appear for $\tau_{1D} = 0$ and $\tau_{1D} = \tau_{1T}$, respectively.
- 3) Mode D may appear for $\tau_{1D} = \tau_{1T}$ and large a/t .
- 4) Figs.6 and 7 show that the strongly reinforced composites with large E_f are not so effective once the microscopic damage initiates.

REFERENCES

Figure 6. Load deformation curves for various (a) L/t ($E_f = 390$ GPa) and (b) E_f ($L/t = 10$) based upon the shear stress criterion $\tau_c = \tau_{IT}$ with the marks for the debonding propagation, a/t .

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Figure 7. Load deformation curves for various (a) L/t ($E_f=390$ GPa) and (b) E_f ($L/t=10$) based upon the energy criterion with $\gamma_B=160$ J/m² and $\tau_{1D}=35$ MPa; the marks indicate the debonding propagation, a/t .

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